

We from the Board of Directors of the
**FEDERATION FOR INTERNATIONAL REFRACTORIES RESEARCH AND
EDUCATION**

Certify that

Murilo Henrique Moreira

*Presented the FIRE short course “Drying of Refractory Castables: From Scientific
Fundamentals to Technological Applications” with 7 hours of duration during the
UNITECR 2023*

Chris Parr

Chairman

FIRE

Executive Secretary

FIRE